

THE EFFECTIVE TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING SPEAKING FOR INTERMEDIATE LEARNERS

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi nutqni o'rgatish usullari qanchalik samarali ekanligini va talabalarning ingliz tilida gapirishda qanchalik muvaffaqiyatli ekanligini o'rganishdir. Shuningdek, ushbu tadqiqot o'rta darajadagi talabalar uchun nutqni o'rgatishda til o'qituvchisining rolini aniqlashga qaratilgan.*

Kalit so`zlar: *Butun vazifani bajarish, muammoni hal qilish, ijtimoiy o'zaro ta'sir, og'zaki o'zaro ta'sir.*

Abstract: *The purpose of this study is to investigate how effective the methods of teaching speaking are, and how successful the students are in speaking English. And also this study aims to find out the role of the language teacher in teaching speaking for intermediate learners.*

Keywords: *Whole-task practice, solve a problem, social interaction, oral interaction.*

Speaking is the most distinguishing feature of human beings from the other living creatures because it is the natural state of language that all human beings are born to speak their native language. In learning a second or foreign language, most of the learners find speaking the most difficult skill to have a success because it needs oral communication that consists of both speaking and listening. Generally speaking, language is a tool of communication. If you cannot speak, all your effort is in vain. Thus we have to give importance to speaking in our English lessons right from the beginning because there is no use of knowledge about a language without having the skill of using it.

Pre-communicative activities can be called as preparatory activities which prepare the learners to communicate. Their target is making the students use the language with desired fluency without thinking of giving the message accurately. "In pre-communicative activities, the teacher isolates specific elements of knowledge or skill which compose communicative ability, and provides the learners with opportunities to practice them separately.

The learners are thus being trained in the part-skills of communication rather than practice the total skill to be acquired".¹

¹ Abbott, G. And Wingard, P. The Teaching of English as an International Language. New York:1992 y,

Communicative activities are designed to alter the pre-communicative knowledge and skills into communicating meanings, which Littlewood calls “whole-task practice”. In considering how people learn to carry out various kinds of skilled performance, it is often useful to distinguish between (a) training in the part-skills of which the performance is composed and (b) practice in the total skill, sometimes called “whole-task practice”.

In foreign language learning our means for providing learners with whole-task practice in the classroom is through various kinds of communicative activity, structured in order to suit the learners’ level of ability.

Communicative activities are also divided into two. Functional communication activities help the students use the language they learned effectively to get meanings. In other words, they are related only to the communication of information. In these activities, “students have to overcome an information gap, get information from someone or somewhere else, or solve a problem”.²

Social interaction activities are role-playing and exploiting simulation. These create a wider variety of social situations and relationships than would otherwise occur. Success is now measured not only in terms of the functional effectiveness of the language, but also in terms of the social acceptability of the forms that are used.

Oral Interaction Activities, Littlewood suggests two types of interaction activities. The first one is functional communication activities and the second is social interaction activities.

There are four basic kinds of functional communication activities.

1. Sharing information with restricted co-operation

- Identifying a picture from a set
- Discovering identical pairs
- Discovering sequences or locations
- Discovering missing information
- Discovering missing features
- Discovering secrets

2. Sharing information with unrestricted co-operation

- Communicating patterns and pictures
- Communicating models
- Discovering differences
- Following directions

3. Sharing and processing information

- Reconstructing story sequences
- Pooling information to solve a problem

4. Processing information

² Littlewood, W. Communicative Language Teaching. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press 1981 y.

- Problem solving tasks³

If the language learners do not learn how to speak or do not get any chance to speak in the language classroom, they may soon get de-motivated and lose interest in learning it. In order to make the classroom a dynamic and a fun place, right activities should be conducted in them.

If we can create such an atmosphere, we can raise general learner motivation. The students who were motivated were more self-confident and less anxious as the result of which they participated actively in class, whereas students who were not motivated were not self-confident and they felt anxious.

The research results show that the students like their teachers and they are happy with the teachers' manners and attitudes towards them.

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